

Investigating the Persistent Current of Zig-Zag (6,0) Single-Walled Carbon Using the Deng-Fan-Hulthen Potential (DFHP)

Ikechukwu Otete

Department of Physics, Faculty of Science Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa state
Nigeria

Article Information

Article # 2008

Received: 10th Jan 2026

1st Revision: 4th Feb. 2026

2nd Revision: 14th Feb. 2026

Acceptance: 28th March 2026

Available Online:

4th March 2026.

Keywords:

Deng-Fan-Hulthen potential,
Persistent current,
Magnetic flux,
Zig-Zag SWCNT,
Nikiforov-Uvarov.

Abstract

Abstract

This study investigates persistent current, a non-dissipative current that flows in superconducting and mesoscopic materials or devices without requiring an external power or voltage source. We utilize the Deng-Fan-Hulthen Potential (DFHP) model, which combines the Deng-Fan and Hulthen potentials in the presence of magnetic and Aharonov-Bohm (AB) flux fields, to explore the behavior of the persistent current in a zig-zag (6,0) single-walled carbon nanotube (SWCNT). The Schrödinger wave equation is solved analytically using the Nikiforov-Uvarov (NU) method, yielding the energy equation and wave function. The energy equation is then used to derive the partition function of the system. From this partition function, the persistent current as a function of magnetic flux is evaluated with respect to temperature, magnetic field, AB flux, and the tube's length and diameter. Graphical plots reveal key features of the persistent current, including its exponential decrease with increasing temperature, its increase with the magnetic field, and its oscillatory behavior in response to the AB flux. Additionally, the persistent current is observed to increase exponentially with tube length and decrease exponentially with nanotube diameter.

*Corresponding Author: Ikechukwu Otete: oteteii@fuotuo.ke.edu.ng

Introduction

The discovery of carbon nanotubes CNTs and fullerenes, with the attendant theoretical research on their properties, has made their importance prominent in nanotechnology (Michael, 2006). Carbon nanotubes possess unique electronic and mechanical properties, amongst others. Their topological nature allows the investigation of persistent current in the presence of applied external fields (Szopa *et al.*, 2004). No doubt, the fascinating properties of CNTs have brought them to the fore of extensive research to fully harness their potential and technological applications.

The ideology of persistent current is traceable to orbital currents in metallic, semiconducting and insulating materials showing diamagnetism in the presence of weak magnetic fields. This phenomenon, which shows some similarities with supercurrent in superconductors, was noticed in mesoscopic objects due to Aharonov-Bohm (AB) flux in high fields (Igor, 2004). Persistent current, regarded as a quantum phenomenon, whose observation is associated with the discovery of superconductivity in 1911 by H. Kamerlingh Onnes, is eddy currents induced by an external field, which are moving inside the filaments

of a superconducting magnet cable (Hélène, 2008; Holzer, 1996). It is seen as a thermal equilibrium property of a minute resistive ring system measurable in a low temperature regime (William, 2011). According to Santanu (2008), Hund, in the tender stage of quantum mechanics, predicted the possibility of persistent current. In mesoscopic metal rings, the first experimental evidence of persistent current was given by Levy and his co-authors. The prediction of it in a mesoscopic metal ring threaded by magnetic flux was made by Buttiker and his co-authors. Also, Tsebro *et al* (1999), observed a persistent current at low temperature in the multi-walled nanotube they synthesised. The synthesised samples had trapped magnetic flux that could be responsible for the persistent current.

Stéphane *et al* (2003) reported that an induced current flows around the circumference of the ring of aromatic molecules when an applied magnetic field to their planes breaks the time reversal symmetry. The flux quantum due to the Aharonov-Bohm effect induces a current known as a persistent current. Persistent current can be observed along the circumference of a cylindrical carbon nanotube when there is a

modulation of its occupied electronic state by varying the external magnetic field. In a closed-loop electronic system, persistent current occurs in response to an applied magnetic field. It takes place when a conducting ring is threaded by magnetic flux (Shyu, 2004). It could be as a result of the presence of quantised and electron states that are delocalized (Szopa *et al.*, 2002). Localised current-carrying electron states exist at the edges of a ring or cylinder kept in a strong region of magnetic field applied perpendicularly to its axis (Avishai *et al.*, 1993).

According to Colin and Jayannavar (2014), current flow in a nano ring when the time reversal symmetry of the system between the left and right mobile charge carriers is broken by magnetic flux. A non-dissipative current can occur when an off-resonating electromagnetic field, which is being propagated along the carbon nanotube (CNT) axis, interacts with the electrons in the nanotube. This current is known as persistent current (Kibis *et al.*, 2021). Persistent currents are induced in a single-walled carbon nanotube by a static magnetic field applied parallel to its axis. They are as a result of the Aharonov-Bohm effect (Szopa *et al.*, 2002). Persistent current is noticed or observed in a toroidal carbon nanotube (TCN) when it is threaded by magnetic flux (Xu *et al.*, 2009). A loop conductor in a magnetic field has a non-dissipative current at its ground state flowing within it without the influence of external voltage. This current is known as persistent current (Igor, 2003).

When the derivative of the free energy, F of the system with respect to the magnetic flux Φ , the expression for persistent current can be written as (Odinstov *et al.*, 1999; Eshghi, 2017) $I = -\delta F/\delta\Phi$. The persistent current $I(\Phi)$ is a periodic function of the flux, $\Phi = h/e$, representing the flux quantum (Mohanty, 1999). Several factors can affect the behaviour or performance of persistent current in mesoscopic material or carbon nanotubes, whether toroidal or cylindrical. Some of the factors include the potential parameters, spherical confinement parameter, the geometries of the toroidal carbon nanotubes or rings, the nature of the defect (as a result of doping) or deformation of the carbon nanotube, the shape of the Fermi surface, magnetic flux, temperature and nature of disorder (Vinod *et al.*, 2023; Zhenhua, 2006; Szopa *et al.*, 2002; Lin and Chuu, 1998). For instance, Zhenhua *et al.*, (2006) investigated the effect of structure deformation and chirality on the electronic structure and persistent current in toroidal carbon nanotubes. And based on the nature of the band gap they classified the carbon nanotube of different chiralities and angles into metallic, semiconductor and insulator. As part of the investigation, the nature or

behaviour of the persistent current of type I and type II carbon nanotube was examined as a function of the magnetic flux and geometric parameters. It was discovered that the magnetic flux showed a unique jump features when the persistent current was plotted against the flux in the case of the metallic and semiconducting tori that were deformed. As the chiral angle approaches $\pm 15^\circ$, the persistent current was very strong. The persistent current varies inversely to the torus radius and does not depend on the torus width. In the deformed regime, there was a dramatic drop in the persistent currents when the strains got to 0.4%. The saw tooth nature of the current became smooth which could fit well to $I = \pm A \sin(2\pi\Phi/\Phi_0)$. As the strain became 1% , the current became almost unnoticed (Lin and Chuu, 1998).

With the spin orbit interaction (SOI) into consideration and in the presence of magnetic field, Vinod *et al.*, (2023), studied how persistent currents and magnetic fields can be enhanced in SiGe quantum rings in an anharmonic axially symmetric potential with a centrifugal core. The authors investigated different cases of induced current and magnetic field with laser pulses both in the presence of Rashba spin-orbit interaction (RSOI) and Dresselhaus spin-orbit interaction (DSOI). And as part of their reports, the induced current, that is the persistent current increased in magnitude in the presence of magnetic field. The increase of temperature in toroidal carbon nanotubes would cause electrons to be in the occupied states above the Fermi level. The persistent current that results in such states flow in the direction that is against the one in the states below the Fermi level. In such situation, there is a cancellation of the current above and below the states in the Fermi level. With the increasing temperature, the persistent current which is flux dependent and oscillatory in nature decreases in amplitude (Lin and Chuu, 1998). According to Sylvain *et al.*, (2003) persistent current in toroidal nanotube can be diminished by increase in temperature. Temperature affects persistent current negatively. It reduces its amplitude (Deo and Jayannavar, 1993; Junjie *et al.*, 1999; Eshghi, 2017). Persistent current is affected by the length and the tube's diameter of carbon nanotubes. Persistent current increases proportionally as the tube's length increases but decreases as the diameter of the tube increases (Szopa *et al.*, 2002).

In this work, we use DFHP to study analytically the persistent current of zig-zag single-walled (6,0) carbon nanotube by examining the effect of this current on the behaviour of the magnetic field, Aharonov-Bohm (AB) flux, the length and the diameter of the carbon nanotube.

Theoretical Model and Methodology

In the cylindrical co-ordinate, for a charged particle moving under the influence of electromagnetic field \vec{B}

$$\frac{1}{2\mu} (\i\hbar\vec{\nabla} - \frac{q}{c}\vec{A})^2 + D_e \left(1 - \frac{\chi}{(e^{\theta r} - 1)}\right)^2 - \frac{V_0 e^{\theta r}}{(1 - e^{-\theta r})} = E_{(n,m)} \psi_{(\rho,\varphi,z)} \tag{1}$$

where $\chi = e^{\theta r} - 1$, D_e is the dissociation energy, r_e is the molecular bond length, r is the internuclear distance, θ , the range of the potential well and V_0 represent the potential strength

For our carbon nanotube, μ is the effective mass. We write the vector potential \vec{A} as $\vec{A} = \vec{A}_1 + \vec{A}_2$. The symmetric or Coulomb gauge is represented as $\nabla \times \vec{A}_1 = \vec{B}$ and $\nabla \times \vec{A}_2 = 0$ where B_z is the applied

Ahanorov-Bohm (AB) flux kept in a region of potential, we write the Hamiltonian as (Otete *et al.*, 2024):

electromagnetic field in the z-direction. The magnetic flux Φ_{AB} is as a result of the solenoid. Therefore, in the cylindrical coordinate system, the vector potential has the azimuthal components written as (Sameer *et al.*, 2014):

$$\vec{A}_1 = \frac{\vec{B}e^{-\theta r}}{(1 - e^{-\theta r})}, \vec{A}_2 = \frac{\Phi_{AB}}{2\pi r} \hat{\Phi} \text{ So, } \vec{A} = \left(0, \frac{\vec{B}e^{-\theta r}}{(1 - e^{-\theta r})} + \frac{\Phi_{AB}}{2\pi r}, 0\right) \tag{2}$$

The DFHP which is our potential comprises of two different potentials-Deng-Fan and Hulthen potentials. We take a wave function in the cylindrical coordinates as:

$$\psi_{(r,\varphi)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{im\varphi} R_{nm}(r) \quad m = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2 \dots \tag{3}$$

Here, m stands for the magnetic quantum number. A second-order differential equation is obtained when we introduce our confining potential, vector potential and the wave function into Eq. (1).

$$\frac{d^2 R_{nm}(r)}{dr^2} + \frac{2\mu}{\hbar^2} \left[E - D_e \left(1 - \frac{\chi}{(e^{\theta r} - 1)}\right)^2 + \frac{V_0 e^{-\theta r}}{(1 - e^{-\theta r})} - \frac{2\hbar m e \delta \vec{B} e^{-\theta r}}{c(1 - e^{-\theta r})} - \frac{e^2 \vec{B} e^{-2\theta r}}{c^2(1 - e^{-\theta r})^2} - \frac{e^2 \vec{B} \Phi_{AB} e^{-\theta r}}{c^2(1 - e^{-\theta r})^2 2\pi r} - \frac{((m + \zeta) - \frac{1}{4})}{r^2} \right] R_{nm}(r) = 0 \tag{4}$$

In order to solve Eq. (4) which has both exponential and radial terms, we introduce the Greene and Aldrich approximation scheme given in Eq. (5) below (Otete *et al.*, 2024):

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \approx \vartheta^2 \left[d_o + \frac{e^{-\theta r}}{(1 - e^{-\theta r})} \right] \tag{5}$$

By inserting Eq. (5) into Eq. (4) we have

$$\frac{d^2 R_{nm}(r)}{dr^2} + \left[\frac{2\mu E}{\hbar^2} - \frac{2\mu D_e}{\hbar^2} + \frac{4\mu D_e \chi e^{-\theta r}}{\hbar^2(1 - e^{-\theta r})} - \frac{2\mu D_e \chi^2 e^{-2\theta r}}{\hbar^2(1 - e^{-\theta r})^2} + \frac{2\mu V_0 e^{-\theta r}}{\hbar^2(1 - e^{-\theta r})} - \frac{2m\eta\theta \vec{B} e^{-\theta r}}{\hbar^2(1 - e^{-\theta r})^2} - \frac{\eta^2 \vec{B}^2 e^{-2\theta r}}{\hbar^2(1 - e^{-\theta r})^2} - \frac{\eta^2 \theta \vec{B} \Phi_{AB} e^{-\theta r}}{\hbar^2(1 - e^{-\theta r})^2 2\pi} - ((m + \zeta) - \frac{1}{4}) \vartheta^2 \left(d_o + \frac{e^{-\theta r}}{(1 - e^{-\theta r})} \right) \right] R_{nm}(r) = 0 \tag{6}$$

Where $\eta = \frac{e}{c}$, $\Phi_o = \frac{\hbar c}{e}$, $\zeta = \frac{\Phi_{AB}}{\Phi_o}$ and $\eta = e^{\theta r} - 1$, c is the speed of light

By employing the transformation $z = e^{-\theta r}$ (7)

After differentiating twice, you will obtain:

$$\frac{d^2}{dz^2} = \frac{\delta^2 z^2 d^2}{dz^2} + \frac{\delta^2 z d}{dz} \tag{8}$$

Substituting Eq. (8) into Eq. (6) and divide through by $\vartheta^2 z^2$ the result will be:

$$\frac{d^2 R_{nm}}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{z} \frac{dR_{nm}}{dz} + \frac{1}{z^2} \left[\frac{2\mu E}{\hbar^2 \vartheta^2} - \frac{2\mu D_e}{\hbar^2 \vartheta^2} + \frac{4\mu D_e \chi z}{\hbar^2 \vartheta^2 (1-z)} - \frac{2\mu D_e \chi^2 z^2}{\hbar^2 \vartheta^2 (1-z)^2} + \frac{2\mu V_0 z}{\hbar^2 \vartheta^2 (1-z)} - \frac{2m\eta \vec{B} S}{\hbar \vartheta (1-z)^2} - \frac{\eta^2 \vec{B}^2 z^2}{\hbar^2 \vartheta (1-z)^2} - \frac{\eta^2 \vec{B} \Phi_{AB} z}{\hbar^2 \vartheta (1-z)^2 \pi} - \left((m + \zeta)^2 - \frac{1}{4} \right) \left(d_o + \frac{z}{(1-z)^2} \right) \right] R_{nm}(r) = 0 \tag{9}$$

For ease, the following dimensionless symbols are used:

$$-\varepsilon = \frac{2\mu(E_{nm} - D_e)}{\hbar^2 \vartheta^2}, \gamma_1 = \frac{4\mu D_e \chi}{\hbar^2 \vartheta^2}, \gamma_2 = \frac{2\mu D_e \chi^2}{\hbar^2 \vartheta^2}, \gamma = \frac{2\mu V_0}{\hbar^2 \vartheta^2}, \beta = \frac{2m\eta \vec{B}}{\hbar \vartheta}, \Lambda_1 = \frac{\eta^2 \vec{B}^2}{\hbar^2 \vartheta^2}, \Lambda_2 = \frac{\eta^2 \vec{B} \Phi_{AB}}{\hbar^2 \vartheta^2 \pi}, V = \left((m + \zeta)^2 - \frac{1}{4} \right) \tag{10}$$

Equation (9) can be rewritten with respect to these dimensionless symbols as:

$$\frac{d^2 R_{nm}}{dz^2} + \frac{(1-z)}{z(1-z)} \frac{dR_{nm}}{dz} + \frac{1}{z^2(1-z)^2} [-\varepsilon(1-z)^2 + \gamma_1(1-z)z - \gamma_2(z^2) + \gamma(1-z)z - \beta(z) - \Lambda_1(z^2) - \Lambda_2(1-z)z - Vd_o(1-z)^2 - V(z)] R_{nm} = 0 \tag{11}$$

Subsequently, Eq. (11) can be evaluated further as:

$$\frac{d^2 R_{nm}}{dz^2} + \frac{(1-z)}{z(1-z)} \frac{dR_{nm}}{dz} + \frac{1}{z^2(1-z)^2} [-(\varepsilon + \gamma_1 + \gamma_1 + \gamma + \Lambda_1 - \Lambda_2 + Vd_o)z^2 + (2\varepsilon + \gamma_1 + \gamma - \beta - \Lambda_2 + 2Vd_o - V)z - (\varepsilon + Vd_o)] R_{nm}(z) = 0 \tag{12}$$

We compared Equation (12) with the parametric form of the NU of Eq. (13) written as (Otete *et al.*, 2024):

$$R'' + \frac{\vartheta_1 - \vartheta_2 z}{z(1 - \vartheta_3 z)} R' + \left[\frac{-\xi_1 z^2 + \xi_2 z - \xi_3}{z^2(1 - \vartheta_3 z)^2} \right] R(z) = 0 \tag{13}$$

The energy eigen values equation according to the NU is written as (Otete, 2023):

$$\vartheta_2 n - (2n + 1)\vartheta_5 + (2n + 1) [\sqrt{\vartheta_9} + \vartheta_3 \sqrt{\vartheta_8}] + n(n - 1) \vartheta_3 + \vartheta_7 + 2\vartheta_3 \vartheta_8 + 2\sqrt{\vartheta_8 \vartheta_9} = 0 \tag{14}$$

The wave function is written as:

$$R_{nm}(z) = z^{\vartheta_{12}} (1 - \vartheta_3 z)^{-\vartheta_{12} - \vartheta_{13}/\vartheta_3} p_n^{\vartheta_{10} - 1, (\frac{\vartheta_{11}}{\vartheta_3}) - (\vartheta_{10} - 1)} (1 - 2\vartheta_3 z) \tag{15}$$

where the following parameters are written as

$$\vartheta_4 = \frac{1}{2} (1 - \vartheta_1) \tag{16}$$

$$\vartheta_5 = \frac{1}{2} (\vartheta_2 - 2\vartheta_3) \tag{17}$$

$$\vartheta_6 = \vartheta_5 + \xi_1 \tag{18}$$

$$\vartheta_7 = 2\vartheta_4 \vartheta_5 - \xi_2 \tag{19}$$

$$\vartheta_8 = \vartheta_4^2 + \xi_3 \tag{20}$$

$$\vartheta_9 = \vartheta_3 \vartheta_7 + \vartheta_3^2 \vartheta_8 + \vartheta_6 \tag{21}$$

$$\vartheta_{10} = \vartheta_1 + 2\vartheta_4 + 2\sqrt{\vartheta_8} \tag{22}$$

$$\vartheta_{11} = \vartheta_2 - 2\vartheta_5 + 2(\sqrt{\vartheta_9} + \vartheta_3 \sqrt{\vartheta_8}) \tag{23}$$

$$\vartheta_{12} = \vartheta_4 + \sqrt{\vartheta_8} \tag{24}$$

$$\vartheta_{13} = \vartheta_5 - (\sqrt{\vartheta_9} + \vartheta_3 \sqrt{\vartheta_8}) \tag{25}$$

When comparison of Eq. (12) is done with the parametric form of the NU of Eq. (13) the following, parameters can be found:

$$\vartheta_1 = \vartheta_2 = \vartheta_3 = 1 \tag{26}$$

$$\xi_1 = \varepsilon + \gamma_1 + \gamma_1 + \gamma + \Lambda_1 - \Lambda_2 + Vd_o \tag{27}$$

$$\xi_2 = 2\varepsilon + \gamma_1 + \gamma - \beta - \Lambda_2 + 2Vd_o - V \tag{28}$$

$$\xi_3 = \varepsilon + Vd_o \tag{29}$$

From Eqs. (16-21) we obtain

$$\vartheta_4 = \frac{1}{2} (1 - \vartheta_1) = 0, \vartheta_5 = \frac{1}{2} (\vartheta_2 - 2\vartheta_3) = -\frac{1}{2}, \vartheta_6 = \vartheta_5 + \xi_1 = \frac{1}{4} + \varepsilon + \gamma_1 + \gamma_1 + \gamma + \Lambda_1 - \Lambda_2 + Vd_o \tag{30}$$

$$\vartheta_7 = 2\vartheta_4 \vartheta_5 - \xi_2 = -(2\varepsilon + \gamma_1 + \gamma - \beta - \Lambda_2 + 2Vd_o - V) \tag{31}$$

$$\vartheta_8 = \vartheta_4^2 + \xi_3 = \varepsilon + Vd_o \tag{32}$$

$$\vartheta_9 = \vartheta_3 \vartheta_7 + \vartheta_3^2 \vartheta_8 + \vartheta_6 = \frac{1}{4} + \beta + V + \Lambda_1 + \gamma_2 \tag{33}$$

$$\text{Recall that in Eq.(10), } -\varepsilon = \frac{2\mu(E_{nm} - D_e)}{\hbar^2 \delta^2} \tag{34}$$

So, substituting Eqs. (30-33) into Eq. (14) and carrying out some algebra, the energy eigenvalue equation of the (DFHP) is obtained as:

$$E_{nm} = -\frac{\hbar^2 \vartheta^2}{2\mu} \left[\left(\frac{(\sigma - \Lambda)}{2(\tau + \sqrt{\sigma})} - \frac{(\tau + \sqrt{\sigma})}{2} \right)^2 - Vd_o + D_e \right] \tag{35}$$

Where

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{4} + \beta + V + \Lambda_1 + \gamma_2, \Lambda = -\gamma_1 - \gamma + \beta + \Lambda_2 + V, \tau = n + \frac{1}{2} \tag{36}$$

Therefore, when we consider the dimensionless symbols of Eq. (10), we rewrite Eq. (36) as:

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{4} + \frac{2m\eta\bar{B}}{\hbar\theta} + (m + \zeta)^2 - \frac{1}{4} + \frac{\eta^2 \bar{B}^2}{\hbar^2 \theta^2} + \frac{2\mu D_e \Omega^2}{\hbar^2 \theta^2} \tag{37}$$

$$\Lambda = -\frac{4\mu D_e \Omega}{\hbar^2 \theta^2} - \frac{2\mu V_0}{\hbar^2 \theta^2} + \frac{2m\eta\bar{B}}{\hbar\theta} + \frac{\eta^2 \bar{B} \Phi_{AB}}{\hbar^2 \theta \pi} + (m + \zeta)^2 - \frac{1}{4} \tag{38}$$

From Eqs. (22-25) we determine

$$\vartheta_{10} = \vartheta_1 + 2\vartheta_4 + 2\sqrt{\vartheta_8} = 1 + 2\sqrt{\varepsilon + Vd_o} \tag{39}$$

$$\vartheta_{11} = \vartheta_2 - 2\vartheta_5 + 2(\sqrt{\vartheta_9} + \vartheta_3 \vartheta_8) = 2 + 2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{4} + \beta + V + \Lambda_1 + \gamma_2 + \varepsilon + Vd_o} \right) \tag{40}$$

$$\vartheta_{12} = \vartheta_4 + \sqrt{\vartheta_8} = \sqrt{\varepsilon + Vd_o} \tag{41}$$

$$\vartheta_{13} = \vartheta_5 - (\sqrt{\vartheta_9} + \vartheta_3\sqrt{\vartheta_8}) = -\frac{1}{2} - \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{4} + \beta + V + \Lambda_1 + \gamma_2} + \sqrt{\varepsilon + Vd_0} \right) \quad (42)$$

Substituting Eqs. (39-42) into Eq. (15) the wave function written in Eq. (43) is obtained.

$$R_{nm}(z) = z^{\sqrt{\varepsilon+Vd_0}} (1-z)^{\frac{1}{2} + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4} + \beta + V + \Lambda_1 + \gamma_2}} P_n^{2\sqrt{\varepsilon+Vd_0}, 2\sqrt{\frac{1}{4} + \beta + V + \Lambda_1 + \gamma_2}} (1-2z) \quad (43)$$

3. The Partition Function, the Thermodynamic Properties and Persistent Current of Carbon Nanotube

We can use the partition function to determine the thermodynamic properties of Deng-Fan-Hulthen Potential (DFHP) of entropy, free energy, mean energy and specific heat capacity. For the persistent current which is temperature dependent, we evaluated it from this mathematical expression (Edet *et al.*, 2020) as:

$$I_{(\beta)} = \frac{-e}{hc} \frac{\delta F(\beta)}{\delta M} \quad (44)$$

At a particular temperature, when a summation is carried out over all energy levels, the partition function can be calculated [26]. We write the partition function as:

$$Z(\beta) = \sum_n^{v_{max}} e^{-\beta E_{n,m}} \quad (45)$$

where $\beta = \frac{1}{kT}$ with k as the Boltzmann constant, T , the temperature E_{nm} is the energy of the n th bound state where $n = 0, 1, 2, 3 \dots, v_{max}$.

We therefore re- write the energy eigen value of equation (35) as:

$$E_{nm} = -\hbar^2 \vartheta^2 \left(\frac{Q_1 - (n+\sigma)^2}{2(n+\sigma)} \right)^2 + Q_2 \quad (46)$$

where

$$Q_1 = \frac{1}{4} + \frac{2m\eta\bar{B}}{\hbar\theta} + (m + \zeta)^2 - \frac{1}{4} + \frac{\eta^2\bar{B}^2}{\hbar^2\vartheta^2} + \frac{2\mu D_e X^2}{\hbar^2\vartheta^2} + \frac{4\mu D_e}{\hbar^2\vartheta^2} - \frac{2\mu V_0}{\hbar^2\vartheta^2} + \frac{2m\eta\bar{B}}{\hbar\theta} + \frac{\eta^2\bar{B}\Phi_{AB}}{\hbar^2\vartheta\pi} + (m + \zeta)^2 - \frac{1}{4} \quad (47)$$

$$Q_2 = \left((m + \zeta)^2 - \frac{1}{4} \right) d_o \left(\frac{\hbar^2\vartheta^2}{2\mu} \right) + D_e \quad (48)$$

Therefore, equation (44) can be re-writing as:

$$Z(\beta) = \sum_n^{v_{max}} e^{-\beta \left[-\frac{\hbar^2\vartheta^2(Q_1 - (n+\sigma)^2)^2}{2\mu} + Q_2 \right]} \quad (49)$$

We use an integral form to replace the summation of equation (49) in the classical limit. Therefore, we have

$$Z_{(\beta)} = \int_0^v e^{\left(Pl^2\beta + \frac{G\beta}{l^2} + M\beta \right)} dl, l = n + \sigma \quad (50)$$

Where

$$P = \frac{\hbar^2\vartheta^2}{8\mu}, G = -\frac{\hbar^2\vartheta^2 Q_1^2}{8\mu}, M = -\left(\frac{\hbar^2\vartheta^2 Q_1}{4\mu} + Q_2 \right) \quad (51)$$

We evaluate Eq. (50) with the aid of Maple software to get the partition function of the system as:

$$\frac{1}{2} e^{P.\beta.l^2 + M.\beta.\sqrt{G.\beta}} \left(\frac{2.v.e^{\frac{G.\beta}{v^2}}}{\sqrt{G.\beta}} - \frac{2\sqrt{G.\beta} \sqrt{\pi} \operatorname{erfi} \left(\frac{G.\beta}{v} \right)}{\sqrt{G.\beta}} - 2\sqrt{\pi} \right) \quad (52)$$

Here $\operatorname{erfi}(k)$ represents the imaginary error function (Edet *et al.*, 2020) define as:

$$\operatorname{erfi}(k) = i\operatorname{erf}(k) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^k e^{t^2} dt \quad (53)$$

For different numerical calculations we use the error function in Maple software.

The plots of the persistent current versus temperature, magnetic field, AB flux, tube's length and diameter are presented in figures 1,2,3,4 and 5 respectively:

Fig. 1: The Plot of Persistent Current versus temperature

Fig. 2: The Plot of Persistent Current versus Magnetic field

Fig. 3: The Plot of Persistent current versus AB flux

Fig. 4: The Plot of Persistent Current versus tube's Length

Fig. 5: The Plot of Persistent Current versus tube's Diameter

Discussion

The persistent current decreases exponentially with increasing temperature due to phonon scattering. As the temperature rises, atomic domains within the nanotube become disordered, leading to a reduction in the persistent current. Figure 2 illustrates an exponential increase in persistent current with the

applied magnetic field. The magnetic field aligns the atomic domains, enhancing the persistent current. Figure 3 shows the relationship between the persistent current and Aharonov-Bohm (AB) flux, where the persistent current exhibits oscillatory behavior. Figure 4 demonstrates an exponential rise in persistent current as the nanotube length increases. The longer nanotube

enhances thermal transport, which promotes phonon-phonon interactions, thereby increasing the persistent current. In Figure 5, the persistent current decreases with an increase in nanotube diameter. As the diameter grows, more phonons participate in the scattering process, leading to a reduction in the persistent current.

Conclusion

Using the Deng-Fan-Hulthen Potential (DFHP), which combines two empirical potentials in the presence of magnetic and Aharonov-Bohm (AB) flux fields, we solved the Schrödinger Wave Equation (SWE) using the Nikiforov-Uvarov (NU) method to derive the energy equation and wave function. With the aid of Maple software, we calculated the partition function and evaluated the persistent current in a zig-zag (6,0) single-walled carbon nanotube (SWCNT). Our graphical analysis revealed that the persistent current decreased exponentially with increasing temperature, while it increased with stronger magnetic fields. The persistent current exhibited oscillatory behavior with the Aharonov-Bohm flux, increased exponentially as the tube's length grew, and decreased exponentially as the nanotube diameter shrank. These findings are consistent with previous literature.

We found that the DFHP model is also applicable for theoretically investigating the persistent current in carbon nanotubes (CNTs), a property that could be useful in magneto-electronics and quantum computing. However, it is important to note that this study does not explore the energy band gap or density of states of the zig-zag (6,0) SWCNT, as the electronic state energies were not analyzed in relation to the persistent current. Additionally, our study is limited to an idealized, impurity-free zig-zag (6,0) SWCNT. In the presence of impurities or dopants, the behavior of the persistent current would likely differ, potentially exhibiting distinct characteristics.

References

Avishai, Y., Hatsugai, Y. and Kohmoto, M. (1993). Persistent Currents and Edges States in a Magnetic Field. *Physical Review B*. Vol. 47, No 15

Colin, B. and Jayannavar, A.M. (2014). Persistent Current in absence of Magnetic Field in Graphene Nanorings: The Ambiguous Role of Inter Valley Scattering. *Applied Physics Letter* 104, 053112.

Edet, C.O. and Ikot, A.N. (2021). Analysis of the Impact of External Fields on the Energy Spectra and Thermo-Magnetic Properties of N₂, I₂, CO, NO and HCL Diatomic Molecules. *Molecular Physics*, DOI: 10.1080/00268976.2021.1957170

Edet, C.O., Okorie, U.S., Osobonye, G., Ikot, A.N., Rampho, G.J. and Sever, R. (2020). Thermal Properties of Deng-Fan-Eckart Potential Model Using Poisson Summation Approach. *Journal of Mathematical Chemistry* 58:989-1013
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10910-020-01107-4>

Eshghi, M. and Mehraban, H. (2017). Study of a 2D Charged Particle Confined by a Magnetic and AB Flux Fields under the Radial Scalar Power Potential. *Eur. Phys. J. Plus* (2017) 132:121 D)I 10.1140/epjp/i2017-11379-x

Hélène, B. (2008). New Clues in the Mystery of Persistent Currents. *American Physical Society*
<https://physics.aps.org>

Holzer B.J. (1996). Impact of Persistent Currents on Accelerator Performance. *Particle Accelerator*, Vol. 55, pp. (461-471)/ 215-225.

Igor O.K. (2010) Persistent Currents Flux Quantization and Magnetomotive Forces in normal Metals and Superconductors. (Review Article). *Low Temp. Phys.* 36, 841; doi: 10.1063/1.3514415

Igor, O.K. (2003). Persistent Currents in Mesoscopic Loops and Networks. *Turk. J Phys.* 27, 395-417

Junjie, L., Gang, Z., and Binglin G. (1999). Persistent Currents in Toroidal Single-Walled Carbon Nanotubes. *J. Mater. Sci Technol.* Vol 15 No 4,

Kibis, O.V. Boev, M.V and Kovalev, V.M. (2021). Optically induced persistent current in carbon nanotubes. *Physical Review B* 103, 24543.

Lin, M.F. and Chuu, D.S. (1998). Persistent Currents in Toroidal Carbon nanotubes. *Physical Review B* Vol. 57 No 11.

Michael Cornell, J.O'. (2006). Carbon Nanotubes: Properties and Applications. CRS press, Inc.,

Mohanty, P. (1999). Persistent Current in normal Metals. *Ann. Phys. (Leipzig)* 8 7-9, 549-558.

Odintsov, A.A, Smit, W. and Yoshioka H. (1999). Persistent Current and Correlation Effects in Carbon Nanotubes. *Europhys. Lett;* 45 (5) pp. 598-604.

Otete I. (2023). The Energy Eigen Values of Iron Selenide (FeSe) Spin in the Presence of Magnetic Field. *WSN* 182 143-155.

Otete, I., Enaroseha, O.O.E., Okunzuwa S.I. and Ejere A.I.I. (2024). Spectra and Thermodynamic Properties of Zig-Zag Single-Walled Carbon Nanotube with Deng-Fan-Hulthen Potential. *Ukr. J. Phys.* 69, No 10, 719 <https://doi.org/10.15407/ujpe69.10.719>

Sameer, M.I., Babatunde J. F. and Majid H. (2014). Nonrelativistic Molecular Models Under External Magnetic and AB Flux Fields. *Annals of Physics*

353282-298.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.aop.2014.11.017>

Santanu, K.M. (2008). Persistent Current in Metallic Rings and Cylinders. arXiv: 0812.

Shyu, F.L. (2014). Modulation of Electric field on Persistent Current of Carbon Nanotubes. *Physics Letters A*. 378 1428-1433.

Singha Deo, P. and Jayannavar, A.M. (1993). Persistent Due to Evanescent Modes. *Modern Physics Letters B*. Vol. 7, No 15 1045-1051.

Stéphane, P. (2003). Interaction effects on Persistent Current of Ballistic Cylindrical Nanostructures. arXiv: Cond-mat/0303277v2

Sylvain, L., Stephan R. and Angel R. (2003). Persistent Currents in Carbon nanotube based rings. *Physical Review B* 67, 165420.

Szopa, M., Margańska, M., Zipper, E. (2002). Persistent Currents in Carbon nanotubes. arXiv: cond-mat/0205184v1

Szopa, M., Margańska, M., Zipper, E. and Lisowski, M. (2004). Coherence of Persistent Currents in

Multiwall Carbon Nanotubes. *Physical Review B*. 70 075406

Tsebro, V.I., Omel'yanovski O.E. and A.P. Moravskii. (1999). Persistent Currents and Magnetic Flux trapping in Fragments of Carbon Deposits containing Multiwalled Nanotubes. *JETP Letters* Vol. 70 No 7

Vinod, P., Monika Arora and Varsha, Y. (2023). Enhancement of Persistent Currents and Magnetic Fields in a two-dimensional Quantum Ring. *Scientific reports* 13:15486 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-42417-2>

Williams, E.S. (2011). Persistent Current in normal Metal Rings. A Dissertation Presented to the Faculty of Graduate School of Yale University.

Xu, N., Ding, J.W and Ma, M.M. (2009). Curvature and External Electric Field effects on the Persistent Current in Chiral Toroidal Carbon nanotubes. *Eur. Phys. J. B* 67, 71-75. DOI:10.1140/epjb/e2009-00003-1

Zhenhua, Z., Jianhui, Y., Ming, Q., Jingcui, P. and Fuliang, X. (2006). Persistent Currents in Carbon Nanotubes: Effects of Structure Deformations and Chirality. *Journal of Applied Physics* 99, 104311; doi:10.1063/1.2199981